

Life Satisfaction: Between Public Organizational Value and Work Engagement

Ridolof W. Batilmurik¹, Robert Noach², David S. Latupeirissa³

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the direct influence of the value of public organizations and the indirect effect of job involvement on lecturer satisfaction at universities in Kupang City. The study used a sample of 98 lecturer respondents. The analysis uses path analysis with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) equations with the help of SmartPLS. The results of the study show that: 1) the value of public organizations has a positive and significant direct effect on life satisfaction and work engagement; 2) work involvement has no significant effect on life satisfaction, and 3) job involvement does not mediate the relationship between public organization values and life satisfaction.

1. Introduction

Lecturers are professional educators who transfer their knowledge and knowledge to the development of science and technology following their competence. In disseminating science and technology, lecturers are required to show performance both individually and in the performance of the organization (college) where they work. Improved performance, both individually/organizational, will undoubtedly impact the assessment of public perceptions of the profession's importance and the lecturer's duties.

Public perception of the teaching profession's values will impact the life satisfaction that is felt and experienced by every lecturer. A study conducted by (Meynhardt et al., 2020) found that the values of public perceptions of an employee's job could shape the employee's life satisfaction. The same study was also proposed by (Greguras & Diefendorff, 2010). Thus,, lecturers need to improve the quality of values perceived by the public for their work and the organization where they work.

¹ Kupang State Polytechnic, Kupang, Indonesia. Email: rudy.morvin@gmail.com

² Kupang State Polytechnic, Kupang, Indonesia. Email: robert.niach95@gmail.com

³ Kupang State Polytechnic, Kupang, Indonesia. Email: latupeirissadavid1@gmail.com

The results of another study also found that the lecturers' job satisfaction was also influenced by how engaged the lecturers were. Studies conducted by (Meynhardt, 2015) and (Saks & Gruman, 2014) found the importance of an employee's involvement in supporting the achievement of organizational goals that impact job satisfaction.

Based on the facts, it is still found that the work involvement of lecturers is still low in improving the performance of higher education institutions. This can be seen from the performance of universities in Kupang City and East Nusa Tenggara Province, which shows that the quality of universities is still low to compete with other universities in Indonesia. The work involvement of lecturers in the form of participation in research activities at the national level, which is low, has an impact on the quality of publications demanded by the government through the Ministry of Education and Culture (publication outputs: reputable national and international journals). These phenomena and facts indicate that lecturers must improve their quality so that they can have an impact on their life satisfaction. This study aims to analyze the effect of the value of public organizations on life satisfaction directly or indirectly through the work involvement of lecturers.

2. Materials and Methods

Value of Public Organization

Public values are based on the concept of public sustainability, closely related to membership behavior in a public organization. Public value refers to the concept proposed by (Meynhardt et al., 2020) about public value in the business world, which implies creating public value in maintaining and increasing employment opportunities to get a pleasant experience in the community and society that helps employee development. Thus, public value is creating value for the common good, an enabling function for individuals.

Work Engagement

Job involvement is a positive feeling, motivation, and work experienced and felt by individuals, which is indicated by enthusiasm, dedication, and appreciation for their work (Schaufeli et al., 2006).

Life Satisfaction

Life satisfaction is overall satisfaction with all the achievements achieved throughout one's life (Bergkvist & Rossiter, 2007).

Value of Public Organization and Life Satisfaction

One of the predictors of life satisfaction is a public value. Research about the relationship between the value of public organizations and life satisfaction has been carried out by many previous scholars, some of which are: (Greguras & Diefendorff, 2010); (May et al., 2004). This relationship is further related to the theory of social identity through studies conducted by (Ashforth & Mael, 1989) and (He & Brown, 2013). Based on this study, the first hypothesis is:

H1: The value of public organizations has a positive effect on lecturer's life satisfaction

Value of Public Organizations and Work Engagement

Previous studies that have found a relationship between public value and job involvement include: Based on this study, the second hypothesis is: (Meynhardt, 2015; Meynhardt et al., 2020), and (Watermeyer, 2012).

H2: The value of public organizations has a positive effect on lecturers' work involvement

Work Engagement and Life Satisfaction

Previous studies that found a relationship between public values and job involvement include: (Erdogan et al., 2012); (Upadyaya et al., 2016); (Mache et al., 2014); (Liu et al., 2019). Based on this study, the third hypothesis is:

H3: The value of public organizations has a positive effect on lecturers' work involvement

Job Involvement as Mediating Public Organization Values and Life Satisfaction

Previous studies placing job involvement were carried out by (Meynhardt et al., 2020), (Meynhardt, 2015), (Saks & Gruman, 2014), and (Schaufeli & Salanova, 2011). Based on this study, the fourth hypothesis is H_4 : Job involvement positively mediates the relationship between the value of public organizations and the life satisfaction of lecturers.

Next, based on theoretical studies and previous studies' results, a conceptual framework of the current research is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Research Framework

Research Method

Type of Research

This type of research is quantitative research with an explanatory approach. Research that uses numbers and statistical calculations to test the hypotheses built (Field, 2013).

Population and Research Sample

The total population in this study was 190 lecturers spread over several universities in Kupang City, both public and private. Based on the 5% Slovin Formula, a sample of 126 lecturers was drawn, the rate of return of the questionnaire was 98 (78%), and the remaining 22% was not returned/damaged.

So that the respondents obtained as many as 98 lecturers. The respondents' profiles are as follows, male as much as 55% and female 79%. Age of respondents: 30-40 years as much as 41%; 41-50 years as much as 48%; 51-60 years as much as 29% and >60 years as much as 16%. Education Level: Masters 69% and Doctoral (31%) Years of work: 0-5 years 7%; 6-10 years as much as 49%; 11-15 years as much as 47%; 16-20 years as much as 21% and 21 years > as much as 11%.

Instrument Measurement

The research instrument in the form of items in the study will be tested for validation and reliability of the variables studied. Measurements of the value of adopting public organizations (Meynhardt et al., 2020) include 1) polite behavior; 2) doing well in his job; 3) contributing to social cohesion, and 4) contributing to the quality of life. Work involvement (Schaufeli et al., 2006), among others: 1) enthusiasm; 2) dedication; and 3) absorption. Life satisfaction refers to the measurement (Bergkvist & Rossiter, 2007), a single item measure of how satisfied one is in general with his/ her life. All instruments were measured using a 5-point Likert scale (Dawes, 2008) with a scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree).

Data Analysis

The descriptive statistical analysis and quantitative analysis using path analysis with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) modeling with SmartPLS version 3.0 program. Partial Least Square (PLS).

3. Results and Discussions

A. Descriptive Analysis

The average answers for each indicator are as follows: The value of public organizations is 3.80 in the excellent category; The average work involvement is 3.98 (good category), and life satisfaction is obtained on average at 3.89 (satisfied). The descriptive results show that the average answers are in the excellent category.

B. Instruments Testing

The instrument testing in SmartPLS uses the validity and reliability values of each construct concerning the Cronbach alpha value and composite reliability, (Fornell & Larcker, 1981) which has a value > 0.70, (Field, 2013). The results of the instrument measurements are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Measurement Model

Variable	VIF	Loading	α	CR	AVE
Value of Public Organization (NOP)			0.86	0.90	0.70
NOP1	1.62	0.75			
NOP2	2.23	0.84			
NOP3	2.30	0.88			
NOP4	2.23	0.85			
Work Engagement (KK)			0.89	0.93	0.82
KK1	2.71	0.89			
KK2	2.76	0.93			

KK3	2.82	0.90			
Life Satisfaction (KH)			1.00	1.00	1.00
KH1 (General)	1.00	1.00			

Data Sources: Primary data, processed by the author, July 2022

C. Structural Model Analysis (Inner Model)

1) R-Square value

The value of R_Square for life satisfaction is 0.781, meaning that the value of public organizations influences the lecturer's life satisfaction by 78.1%, and the rest is influenced by other factors (21.9%). Meanwhile, the value of R_Square for work involvement is 0.396. It means that the value of public organizations contributes 39.6% to the work involvement of lecturers.

2) Direct and indirect effect

Tests of direct and indirect effects are presented in table 2 below.

Table 2. Direct and Indirect Effect

Relationship of Variables	Path Coefficient	t-stat	P-Val.	Note
<i>NOP</i> → <i>KH</i>	0.861	19.289	0.000	Sig
<i>NOP</i> → <i>KK</i>	0.629	8.4205	0.000	Sig
<i>KK</i> → <i>KH</i>	0.036	0.789	0.430	Not Sig
<i>NOP</i> → <i>KK</i> → <i>KH</i>	0.023	0.751	0.453	Not Sig

Source: Primary data processed, July 2022.

The test results in the final model as presented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Inner and Outer Model

*Discussion**A. Effect of Organizational Public Value on Life Satisfaction*

The value of public organizations has a direct and positive effect on life satisfaction (Table 2). The results showed that the better the value of public organizations owned by lecturers, the higher the life satisfaction of lecturers. These results support previous studies by (Greguras & Diefendorff, 2010); (May et al., 2004). This relationship is further related to the theory of social identity through studies conducted by (Ashforth & Mael, 1989) and (He & Brown, 2013). Regarding these results, if the value of public organizations is in the form of carrying out work well, behaving politely and being able to build social relations with the community, and having a good quality of life from each lecturer, it will have a strong influence on the satisfaction of the lecturer as stated by research conducted by (Ashforth & Mael, 1989) and (He & Brown, 2013).

B. Effect of Organizational Public Value on work engagement

The test results show that the value of public organizations has a positive and significant direct effect on life satisfaction. This study is in line with previous research conducted by: (Meynhardt et al., 2020), (Meynhardt, 2015), and (Watermeyer, 2012). Thus, if the organizational values owned by lecturers are improved, it will increase the work involvement of lecturers.

C. Effect of Work Engagement on Life Satisfaction

Job involvement in this study did not affect the lecturer's life satisfaction. The results of this study are different from studies conducted by: (Erdogan et al., 2012); (Upadyaya et al., 2016); (Mache et al., 2014); (Liu et al., 2019). The findings of this study indicate that although the high work involvement shown by the lecturers does not affect the lecturer's life satisfaction. Several findings were identified, including 1) lecturers have not shown dedication in carrying out their duties professionally; 2) the profession carried out by lecturers is only routine; 3) irrelevant rules in supporting lecturer productivity.

D. Work Engagement as mediating relationship organizational public Value on Life Satisfaction

The results showed that job involvement did not mediate the relationship between the value of public organizations and the life satisfaction of lecturers. These results are different from previous studies conducted by: (Meynhardt et al., 2020); (Meynhardt, 2015); (Saks & Gruman, 2014), and (Schaufeli & Salanova, 2011). These results indicate that job involvement is not a mediator but an independent variable that directly affects life satisfaction.

4. Conclusion

Based on the analysis conducted above, it is concluded as follows. 1) The value of public organizations has a direct and positive effect on life satisfaction and work engagement. 2) Work involvement has no effect on the lecturer's life satisfaction, and 3) job involvement does not mediate the relationship between public organization values and life satisfaction. As the results showed that work involvement did not directly or indirectly affect life satisfaction, thus, it is necessary to conduct an in-depth study of the work involvement of lecturers as an independent variable that also influences lecturer satisfaction by expanding on other factors in future research.

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